

Comparative Study on Academic Achievement and Achievement Motivation of Athletic and Nonathletic Students of District Shopian

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Abstract

Academic achievement is the outcome of education the extent to which a student, teacher or institution has achieved their educational goals. The present study evaluated the Achievement Motivation and Academic Achievement of Athletic and Nonathletic College going Student of Shopian district. To achieve the purpose of the study a total of 120 (60 male & 60 female) subjects were selected. 60 non athlete subjects (30 male and 30 female) were selected by simple random sampling & 60 athlete subjects (30 male & 30 female) were chosen by purposive random sampling method wherein people who had atleast played district level in their respective game and were continuously playing their respective game. There is a significant difference in achievement motivation between athlete males and non-athlete males. It can be concluded that achievement motivation is more in athlete males than non-athlete males. There is a significant difference in achievement motivation between athlete females and non-athlete females. It can be concluded that achievement motivation is more in athlete females than non-athlete females. There is a significant difference in academic achievement between athlete males and non-athlete males. It can be concluded that academic achievement is more in athlete males than non-athlete males. There is a significant difference in academic achievement between athlete females and non-athlete females. It can be concluded that academic achievement is more in athlete females than non-athlete females. There is a significant difference in academic achievement between athlete females and non-athlete males. It can be concluded that academic achievement is more in athlete females than non-athlete males. There is no significant difference in achievement motivation and academic achievement between athlete males and athlete females.

Introduction

Academic life is one of the most important aspects of one's lives that have a high influence on other aspects of life. Several factors can influence academic performance in that education specialists have divided these factors into four categories: individual, family, social and academic factors. All sports involve physical and mental activities that are pursued for more than simply utilitarian reasons. For instance, running, when done as a sport, occurs for reasons beyond simply moving from one place to another. Success and failure are both parts of sports as well as life. A sportsman knows that there will be times when he will win matches; there will also be times when he will lose them. A sportsperson knows how to handle defeat and thus, treats success and failure equally. This is an important life lesson too, which sports can teach a person. Besides this, another importance of sports for children or for adults is that it teaches them how to handle competition, and be fearless when facing the adversaries "Motivation is based on your emotions and achievement-related goals. Achievement motivation is based on reaching success and achieving all of our aspirations in life.

Academic achievement is the outcome of education the extent to which a student, teacher or institution has achieved their educational goals. Academic achievement is commonly measured by examinations or continuous assessment but there is no general agreement on how it is best tested or which aspects are most important procedural knowledge such as skills or declarative knowledge such as facts. Individual differences in academic performance have been linked to differences in intelligence and personality. Students with higher mental ability as demonstrated by IQ tests and those who are higher in conscientiousness (linked to effort and achievement motivation) tend to achieve highly in academic settings. A recent meta-analysis suggested that mental curiosity has an important influence on academic achievement in addition to intelligence and conscientiousness. Children's semi-structured home learning environment transitions into a more structured learning environment when children start first grade. Early academic achievement enhances later academic achievement. Parent's academic socialization is a term describing the way parents influence students academic achievement by shaping students' skills, behaviors and attitudes towards school. Parent influence students through the environment and discourse parents have with their children. Academic socialization can be influenced by parents' socio-economic status. Highly educated parents tend to have more stimulating learning environments. Children's' first few years of life are crucial to the development of language and social skills. School preparedness in these areas help students adjust to academic

expectancies. Another very important enhancer of academic achievement is the presence of physical activity. Studies have shown that physical activity can increase neural activity in the brain. Exercise specifically increases executive brain functions such as attention span and working memory. It is important for both parents, and educators, to understand why promoting and encouraging academic motivation from an early age is imperative. Academic motivation is crucial to a student's academic success at any age. Because students form self-concepts, values, and beliefs about their abilities at a young age, the development of early academic motivation has significant implications for later academic careers. A great deal of research has found that students high in academic motivation are more likely to have increased levels of academic achievement and have lower dropout rates. At this point, the significance of early academic motivation to future academic success should be clear. However, different types of academic motivation have different implications for academic achievement. If a student has high levels of academic motivation, knowing whether that student is extrinsically or intrinsically motivated may be important in making predictions about that student's academic career, for the pleasure of learning, rather than for external rewards. In contrast, those who are extrinsically motivated to learn are motivated to learn for external rewards that learning will bring. The present study evaluated the Achievement Motivation and Academic Achievement of Athletic and Nonathletic College going Student of Shopian district.

Methodology

The purpose of the study was to compare the achievement motivation and academic achievement between athletes and non-athletes of Shopian District. To achieve the purpose of the study a total of 120 (60 male & 60 female) subjects were selected. 60 non athlete subjects (30 male and 30 female) were selected by simple random sampling & 60 athlete subjects (30 male & 30 female) were chosen by purposive random sampling method wherein people who had at least played district level in their respective game and were continuously playing their respective game.

The variables were selected after the investigator had gone deep through the available literature and had long and exhausting discussions with various experts in the field, senior faculty members, fellow researchers and research supervisor.

Achievement motivation was measured by administering the achievement motivation questionnaire developed by J.Raven, J.C.Raven and J.H.Court. & academic achievement was measured by aggregate of three year percentage.

The data collected for the current study was analyzed by using descriptive statistics (Mean, Standard Deviation etc) and one way ANOVA. The statistical techniques were analysed by using SPSS software version 22.

RESULTS

The analysis of the data pertaining to the study is presented in this chapter. The study was designed to compare the achievement motivation and academic achievement in athletes and non athletes of Shopian District. To achieve the purpose of the study a total of 120 (60 male & 60 female) subjects were selected. 60 non athlete subjects (30 male and 30 female) were selected by simple random sampling & 60 athlete subjects (30 male & 30 female) were chosen by purposive random sampling method wherein people who had atleast played district level in their respective game and were continuously playing their respective game. The variables were selected after the investigator had gone deep through the available literature and had long and exhausting discussions with various experts in the field, senior faculty members, fellow researchers and research supervisor. The investigator also consulted some senior research scholars who had done research in this field. Achievement motivation and academic achievement were selected as variables for the study. Achievement motivation was measured by administering the achievement motivation questionnaire developed by J.Ravan, J.C.Raven and J.H.Court. & academic achievement was measured by aggregate of three year percentage .The investigator explained the purpose of the study to the subjects in order to get their cooperation as well as to obtain reliable data. It took almost a week to convince the subjects. The subjects were verbally motivated to fill the questionnaires with almost sincerity. The data collected for the current study was analyzed by using descriptive statistics (Mean, Standard Deviation etc) and one way ANOVA. The statistical techniques were analysed by using SPSS software version 22.

ANALYSIS OF THE DATA

Table 1: Achievement Motivation

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Athlete Males	30	27.4333	4.58396	0.83691
Non Athlete Males	30	25.0667	3.94735	0.72069
Athlete female	30	27.2333	4.62141	0.84375
Non Athlete Females	30	24.8333	4.37141	0.79811
Total	120	26.1417	4.49705	0.41052

Table No-1 shows that Mean and Standard deviation values of Achievement Motivation of Athlete Males, Non Athlete Males, Athlete female and Non Athlete Females. The graphical representation of mean values Achievement Motivation of Athlete Males, Non Athlete Males, Athlete female and Non Athlete Females.

Table2: ne way ANOVA

Achievement Motivation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	171.825	3	57.275	2.973	.035
Within Groups	2234.767	116	19.265		
Total	2406.592	119			

From table no. 2 after applying a one way ANOVA results revealed that there were Significant differences in Achievement Motivation between the three groups, $F(3, 116) = 2.973, p < 0.05$.

Hoc Tests

LSD: Multiple Comparisons

(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Athlete Males	Non Athlete Males	2.36667*	1.13329	.039
	Athlete female	.20000	1.13329	.860
	Non Athlete Females	2.60000*	1.13329	.024
Non-Athlete Males	Athlete Males	-2.36667*	1.13329	.039
	Athlete female	-2.16667	1.13329	.058
	Non Athlete Females	.23333	1.13329	.837
Athlete female	Athlete Males	-.20000	1.13329	.860
	Non Athlete Males	2.16667	1.13329	.058
	non Athlete Females	2.40000*	1.13329	.036
Non-Athlete Females	Athlete Males	-2.60000*	1.13329	.024
	Non Athlete Males	-.23333	1.13329	.837
	Athlete female	-2.40000*	1.13329	.036

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

From table no. 3 we can see what LSD comparisons revealed about the mean scores. In Athlete males (M= 27.4333) mean of Achievement Motivation was significantly higher than non-athlete males (M= 25.0667) and non-athlete males. In Athlete females (M= 27.2333) mean of Achievement Motivation was significantly higher than non-athlete females (M= 24.8333).

Table 4: Descriptive statistics of Academic Achievement

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Athlete Males	30	63.5667	5.78156	1.05556
Non AthleteMales	30	57.2333	6.87666	1.25550
Athlete female	30	63.2000	8.58788	1.56793
Non AthleteFemales	30	55.1333	7.63717	1.39435
Total	120	59.7833	8.09314	.73880

Table No-1 shows that Mean and Standard deviation values of Academic Achievement of Athlete Males, Non Athlete Males, Athlete female and Non Athlete Females. The graphical representation of mean values Academic Achievement of Athlete Males, Non Athlete Males, Athlete female and Non Athlete Females.

Table 5: One way ANOVA

Academic Achievement	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1623.367	3	541.122	10.172	.000
Within Groups	6171.000	116	53.198		
Total	7794.367	119			

From table no. 5 after applying a one way ANOVA results revealed that there were

Significant differences in Academic Achievement between the three groups, $F(3, 116) = 2.973, p < 0.05$.

Table 6: Post Hoc Tests. LSD: Multiple Comparisons

(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference(I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Athlete Males	Non Athlete Males	6.33333*	1.88323	.001
	Athlete female	.36667	1.88323	.846
	Non Athlete Females	8.43333*	1.88323	.000
Non AthleteMales	Athlete Males	-6.33333*	1.88323	.001
	Athlete female	-5.96667*	1.88323	.002
	Non Athlete Females	2.10000	1.88323	.267
Athlete female	Athlete Males	-.36667	1.88323	.846
	Non Athlete Males	5.96667*	1.88323	.002
	non Athlete Females	8.06667*	1.88323	.000
Non Athlete Females	Athlete Males	-8.43333*	1.88323	.000
	Non Athlete Males	-2.10000	1.88323	.267
	Athlete female	-8.06667*	1.88323	.000

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

From table no. 6 we can see what LSD comparisons revealed about the mean scores. In Athlete males (M= 63.5667) mean of Academic Achievement was significantly higher than non-athlete males (M= 57.2333) and non-athlete females. In Athlete females (M=) mean of Academic Achievement was significantly higher than non-athlete males (M=63.2000) and non-athlete females (M= 55.1333).

Discussion

Academic life is one of the most important aspects of one's lives that have a high influence on other aspects of life. Several factors can influence academic performance in that education specialists have divided these factors into four categories: individual, family, social and academic factors. All sports involve physical and mental activities that are pursued for more than simply utilitarian reasons. For instance, running, when done as a sport, occurs for reasons beyond simply moving from one place to another. Success and failure are both parts of sports as well as life. A sportsman knows that there will be times when he will win matches; there will also be times when he will lose them. A sportsperson knows how to handle defeat and thus, treats success and failure equally. This is an important life lesson too, which sports can teach a person. Besides this, another importance of sports for children or for adults is that it teaches them how to handle competition, and be fearless when facing the adversaries "Motivation is based on your emotions and achievement-related goals. Achievement motivation is based on reaching success and achieving all of our aspirations in life.

The present study has been conducted to investigate the difference between Achievement Motivation and Academic Achievement between Athletic & Nonathletic College going Students in Shopian District of Kashmir Valley. It was found that the academic motivation of athletes was higher than that of non-athletes. Moreover it was also clear that academic achievement of athletes is better than that of non-athletes. As far as the gender is concerned athlete of both the genders surpassed their non-athletes counterparts in both the variables. However the male gender athletes and non-athletes outclassed their counterpart female gender athletes and nonathletes in both the variables

Conclusions

1. There is a significant difference in achievement motivation between athlete males and non-athlete males. It can be concluded that achievement motivation is more in athlete males than non-athlete males.
2. There is a significant difference in achievement motivation between athlete females and non-athlete females. It can be concluded that achievement motivation is more in athlete females than non-athlete females.

3. There is a significant difference in academic achievement between athlete males and non-athlete males. It can be concluded that academic achievement is more in athlete males than non-athlete males.
4. There is a significant difference in academic achievement between athlete females and non-athlete females. It can be concluded that academic achievement is more in athlete females than non-athlete females.
5. There is a significant difference in academic achievement between athlete females and non-athlete males. It can be concluded that academic achievement is more in athlete females than non-athlete males.
6. There is no significant difference in achievement motivation and academic achievement between athlete males and athlete females.

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